

Proceedings of the
6th Brazilian Conference on Composite Materials

ISBN 978-65-00-49386-3

Part of ISSN 2316-1337

Organised & Edited by R.J. da Silva & T.H. Panzera

Content available at: doi.org/10.29327/566492

Modelling the effect microscale residual stress on acoustoelasticity in carbon fiber composites – Part A: theoretical background

DMG Oliveira^{(a), *}, VV Gonçalves^(b), AA Santos Jr.^(c)

(a) 0000-0001-8675-461x (State University of Campinas – Brazil)

(b) 0000-0002-7355-2979 (Federal University of Ceará – Brazil)

(c) 0000-0001-5786-3673 (State University of Campinas – Brazil)

* Corresponding author: dmoliveira@fem.unicamp.br

Keywords: acoustoelasticity, ultrasound, longitudinal waves, hygrothermal effect, residual stresses.

Abstract: This study presents the formulation for the propagation of ultrasonic waves in a unidirectional composite material made of carbon fiber (HexTow® AS4/HexPly® 8552), widely used in the aeronautical industry. Understanding the mechanisms governing propagation is fundamental for employing ultrasonic technique to measure mechanical stresses in aeronautical components made of composites, using acoustoelasticity. The approach adopted consists of estimating velocity for different fiber angles and, with these estimates, validating the theoretical model to be proposed. Thus, the study is subdivided into two parts, the objective of part A is to propose an ultrasonic wave propagation equation that considers the longitudinal and transverse acoustoelastic constants instead of the third-order elastic constants individually, the deformations and hygrothermal mechanical stresses based on the classical theory of laminates, considering the orientation of the fiber of the composite material. Part B compares the analytical model and the experimental results. Reasonable alternatives were proposed as methods of adjustment, and the correction that considers the cross-sectional thermal stresses was found to be the best one. The possible sources of variation found include the residual stress generated during the curing process. The results indicate that the model is able to describe the phenomenon and that this thermal component of deformation generates stresses that considerably affect the wave velocity.

Fundings: This study was partially funded by the São Paulo Research Foundation – FAPESP, grant number 21616-0 and CNPq, grant 315304/2018-9

1. Introduction

Ultrasound is a viable alternative for use with Structural Health Monitoring (SHM), as its cost is low compared with other techniques such as X-rays and magnetic particles. It is also relatively easy to operate. In recent decades,

Tiradentes, Minas Gerais, Brazil

14-18th August 2022

Copyright © 2022 Authors retain the copyright of this article.

the development of approaches involving ultrasonic waves that use acoustoelasticity has intensified. The approach relates the velocity of propagation of waves to the elastic properties of materials, stresses and residual stresses. The modern foundations of this approach were developed and can be found in the references [1–5].

Stress measurement using acoustoelasticity is an important application of SHM, since structural failures occur mostly due to the emergence of stresses above the limit that the material can withstand. Longitudinal waves are the best suited to measure this parameter in many applications because they are more stress-sensitive [6].

The Part A of this study aims to propose a model capable of describing the propagation of acoustoelastic waves in orthotropic media, applying it to laminated materials to estimate the velocity of longitudinal waves. The classical laminate theory and the theory of elasticity [7] were used to estimate the second-order elastic constants and the stresses, while the theory of acoustoelasticity was used with the hygro-thermo-mechanical effect to estimate the acoustoelastic constants.

In short, a wave propagation model that unifies the classical wave propagation equations, the theory of elasticity, the classical laminate theory, the hygrothermal (thermal) effect, and the theory of acoustoelasticity is proposed to verify how each of the effects represented by these approaches influences the deformations/stresses generated in the manufacturing process.

The development of models that use the acoustoelastic constants and the second and third-order elastic constants for the correct prediction of wave velocity is necessary to achieve the objectives of the study. The hypothesis is that the correction of the hygrothermal effect may help predict these velocities and, consequently, the applied and residual stresses in the materials when measured by ultrasound.

The classical Christoffel's equation for anisotropic media correlates the three velocity wave modes (longitudinal, vertical shear and horizontal shear) with the second-order elastic constants of the material [8]. For longitudinal waves, the Christoffel's tensor can be simplified, resulting in Eq. 1,

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{C_{11}}{\rho}}, \quad (1)$$

where V is longitudinal waves, C_{ij} is the second-order elastic constant and ρ specific mass of the material. However, the effect of stress on the wave velocity is related to third-order elastic constants. For orthotropic materials, the formulation commonly used is the one proposed by Pao and Gamer [5], shown in Eq. (2).

$$\rho V^2 = C_{11} + (4C_{11} + C_{111})e_{11} + C_{112}e_{22} + C_{113}e_{33} + \sigma_{11} \quad (2)$$

With C_{ijk} the third-order elastic constants in the initial coordinate system, e_{ij} is the normal strain at i , in direction j , and σ_{ij} is the normal stress at i , in direction j . Composite materials are heterogeneous by definition. Thus, they do not have elastic constants as defined for metals. However, when the wavelength used in the inspection is much larger than the ply thickness and the fiber diameter, composites can be considered homogeneous. Then the second-order elastic constants can be calculated using the classical laminate theory, as detailed by Jones [7].

Notwithstanding, the mechanical analysis is not sufficient to describe the behavior of waves in laminates when the curing temperature is different from the working temperature, as in the case of a thermoset polymer matrix,

especially in carbon-epoxy fiber, in which the material is susceptible to change in moisture and temperature [7]. This effect is called the Hygro-Thermo-Mechanical effect. The explanation for the thermal effect is that the coefficients of thermal expansion show different values for fibers and matrix. The hygroscopic effect is explained by the tendency of carbon fiber to absorb moisture and, in this process, suffer deformations and stresses. To consider these effects, the terms of the thermal and hygroscopic stresses for composites must be considered in the ABBD Matrix, according to Eq (3):

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ T_{xy} \\ M_x \\ -M_y \\ -M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{61} & A_{62} & A_{66} & B_{61} & B_{62} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{61} & B_{62} & B_{66} & D_{61} & D_{62} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{0x} \\ \epsilon_{0y} \\ \gamma_{0xy} \\ k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{bmatrix} - \Delta T \begin{bmatrix} \overline{\alpha E h_x} \\ \overline{\alpha E h_y} \\ \overline{\alpha E h_{xy}} \\ \overline{\alpha E h_x^2} \\ \overline{\alpha E h_y^2} \\ \overline{\alpha E h_{xy}^2} \end{bmatrix} - \Delta c \begin{bmatrix} \overline{\beta E h_x} \\ \overline{\beta E h_y} \\ \overline{\beta E h_{xy}} \\ \overline{\beta E h_x^2} \\ \overline{\beta E h_y^2} \\ \overline{\beta E h_{xy}^2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

In these matrices in (3), N_x is the force by length [N/m] in direction x of the laminate; N_y is the force by the length in direction y; N_{xy} is the shear-force by the length in the laminate size; M_x is the bending by length [Nm/m] in the laminate in direction x, M_y is the bending by length in direction y; M_{xy} torsion by the length in the laminate; ϵ_{0x} is the middle plane strain in the direction x [m/m]; ϵ_{0y} is the middle plane strain in the direction y; γ_{0xy} is the middle plane shear strain; k_x is the bending strain in the direction x [m-1]; k_y is the bending strain in the direction y; k_{xy} is the shear strain in the xy plane; A_{ij} is the element ij of composite stiffness matrix; B_{ij} is the element ij of composite coupling matrix (normal/bending); and D_{ij} is the element ij of composite matrix stiffness out of the middle plane, ΔT is the thermal variation, Δc is the moisture variation, $\overline{\alpha E h}$ is the thermal stiffness, and $\overline{\beta E h}$ is the moisture stiffness. Details about Eq (3) can be found in Jones [7].

As mentioned before, the theory of acoustoelasticity [1–6], establishes the relationship between the velocity of the ultrasonic wave and the stress applied to materials. This study focuses on longitudinal waves. The variations in the velocity of longitudinal waves are more sensitive to the application of stress in the direction of the wave propagation in metals [6], which can also be considered for composites. The relation between the variation of longitudinal wave velocities when the stress in the body varies is expressed by Eq. (4),

$$\Delta\sigma_1 = \frac{E_1}{L_{11}^1} \frac{(V - V_0)}{V_0}. \quad (4)$$

Where $\Delta\sigma_1$ is the stress variation in direction 1; E_1 is the Young Modulus in direction 1; L_{11}^1 is the acoustoelastic constant, where overwriten index 1 is the direction of the applied stress and underwriten index 11 describes the direction of polarization 1 and propagation of the wave 1, respectively. Besides, V_0 is the reference propagation velocity, and V is the wave velocity.

When stress is applied to direction 1, and the longitudinal wave propagates in direction 1, the acoustoelastic constant is defined as shown in Eq. (5)

$$\frac{dV_1^1/V_1^1}{d\epsilon} = L_{11}^1. \quad (5)$$

When stress is applied to direction 2, and the longitudinal wave propagates in direction 1, a similar relationship is valid, expressed in Eq. (6). The variables are the same as equation (4), but considering the stress in the perpendicular direction 2.

$$\Delta\sigma_2 = \frac{E_2}{L_{11}^2} \frac{(V - V_0)}{V_0}, \tag{6}$$

In the case of plane stress [9], Eq. (7) is used

$$\frac{(V - V_0)}{V_0} = \frac{L_{11}^1}{E_1} \sigma_1 + \frac{L_{11}^2}{E_2} \sigma_2. \tag{7}$$

2. Methodology: Modeling the wave propagation.

Pao and Gamer’s equation for longitudinal waves [4,5] was introduced in Eq. (2). considering that the terms $e_{11} = \varepsilon_1 - \nu_{12}\varepsilon_2 - \nu_{13}\varepsilon_3 + \eta_{16}\gamma_6$, $e_{22} = -\nu_{21}\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 - \nu_{23}\varepsilon_3 + \eta_{26}\gamma_6$, $e_{33} = -\nu_{31}\varepsilon_1 - \nu_{32}\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 + \eta_{36}\gamma_6$ and $\sigma_{11} = C_{11}\varepsilon_1 + C_{12}\varepsilon_2 + C_{13}\varepsilon_3 + C_{16}\gamma_6$, where ε_i is the strain at i direction, ν_{ij} is the Poisson ratio of orthotropic materials, η_{ij} are the coupling coefficients tension-bending, and γ_i is the shear strain. Eq. (2) allows building Eq. (8) after distributing and grouping the deformation terms and knowing that the total deformation is the sum of the mechanical (m-index), thermal (t-index) and hygroscopic (h-index) deformation.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho V^2 = & C_{11} + (\varepsilon_{m1} + \varepsilon_{t1} + \varepsilon_{h1})(5C_{11} + C_{111} - \nu_{21}C_{112} - \nu_{31}C_{113}) \\ & + (\varepsilon_{m2} + \varepsilon_{t2} + \varepsilon_{h2})(- \nu_{12}(4C_{11} + C_{111}) + (C_{112} + C_{12}) - \nu_{32}C_{113}) \\ & + (\varepsilon_{m3} + \varepsilon_{t3} + \varepsilon_{h3})(- \nu_{13}(4C_{11} + C_{111}) - \nu_{23}C_{112} + (C_{113} + C_{13})) \\ & + (\gamma_{m6} + \gamma_{t6} + \gamma_{h6})(\eta_{16}(4C_{11} + C_{111}) + \eta_{26}C_{112} + \eta_{36}C_{113} + C_{16}). \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Now, considering $M_1 = (5C_{11} + C_{111} - \nu_{21}C_{112} - \nu_{31}C_{113})$, $M_2 = (-\nu_{12}(4C_{11} + C_{111}) + (C_{112} + C_{12}) - \nu_{32}C_{113})$, $M_3 = (-\nu_{13}(4C_{11} + C_{111}) - \nu_{23}C_{112} + (C_{113} + C_{13}))$, $M_6 = (\eta_{16}(4C_{11} + C_{111}) + \eta_{26}C_{112} + \eta_{36}C_{113} + C_{16})$, isolating V , knowing that while adopting that i can assume values of 1, 2, 3, and 6, and that k can be m (mechanical), t (thermal), or h (hygroscopic), the Eq. (9) is obtained.

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{C_{11}}{\rho} + \frac{M_i}{\rho} \varepsilon_{ki}}. \tag{9}$$

Deriving the velocity expression with respect to deformation dividing it by the velocity, and adopting $C_{11} \gg M_i \varepsilon_i$, the acoustoelastic constants are obtained from the relation expressed in Eq. (10).

$$\frac{dV/V}{d\varepsilon_{ki}} = \frac{\frac{M_i}{2\rho \left(\frac{C_{11} + M_i \varepsilon_{ki}}{\rho}\right)^{1/2}}}{\left(\frac{C_{11} + M_i \varepsilon_{ki}}{\rho}\right)^{1/2}} = \frac{M_i}{2(C_{11} + M_i \varepsilon_{ki})} = \frac{M_i}{2C_{11}} = L_{11}^{ki}, \tag{10}$$

Rearranging Eq. (10) is possible to relate M_i terms to acoustoelastic constant L_{11}^{ki} , according to Eq. (11).

$$M_i = 2C_{11}L_{11}^{ki}, \tag{11}$$

Substituting equation (11) in (9) gives Eq. (12).

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{C_{11}}{\rho} + \frac{2C_{11}L_{11}^{ki}}{\rho} \varepsilon_{ki}}. \tag{12}$$

The following assumptions were considered to simplify Eq. (12). Firstly, the composite material is free of loading and, therefore, its mechanical deformation is zero. Furthermore, the time to produce hygroscopic deformation is much longer than the time of thermal and mechanical deformations, of the order of years under significant absorption conditions [7]. Thus, the source of all deformation in the sample will be related to thermal effects. Besides, in thin composite materials, stresses and deformations in orientation 3 are negligible. Also, any existing shear stresses do not significantly change the velocity of longitudinal waves [10], i.e., $L_{11}^{t6} = 0$, since no shear stresses were applied. Therefore:

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{C_{11}}{\rho} + \frac{2C_{11}}{\rho} (L_{11}^{t1}\varepsilon_{t1} + L_{11}^{t2}\varepsilon_{t2})}. \tag{13}$$

3. Results and Discussions

In Eq. (12) elastic constant C_{11} can be obtained based on the classical laminate theory [7] for fiber orientation angles between -90° and 90° . Acoustoelastic constants L_{11}^{t1} and L_{11}^{t2} were obtained by equations (4) and (6), respectively, from the stresses and thermal deformations.

For the estimation of the thermal stresses and deformations, the classical laminate theory (hygro-thermo-mechanical effect) was used according to Jones [7]. For this the following hypothesis can be adopted: First, The material is not subjected to any mechanical stress. Second, the hygroscopic deformations and stresses are negligible. Third, the material is unidirectional and has a medium plane of symmetry, so matrix $B=0$. Finally, the momentum flow was neglected as there is no mechanical effort. Thus, the thermal deformations and stresses can be estimated by equations (14) and (15), which are the simplifications of Eq. (3), considering the above hypotheses with the classical laminate theory:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \Delta T \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_x \\ \alpha_y \\ \alpha_{xy} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{14}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = -\Delta T \begin{bmatrix} \overline{\alpha E_1} \\ \overline{\alpha E_2} \\ \overline{\alpha E_3} \end{bmatrix}. \tag{15}$$

In the previous equations, α_i are the thermal coefficients and $\overline{\alpha E_i}$ is the thermal stiffness. The purpose of this part of the work was to establish a model capable of describing the propagation of acoustoelastic waves in orthotropic media. The estimative of longitudinal wave velocity of laminated materials was completely satisfied by applying Eq. 12 and 13 along with Eq. 14 and 15.

4. Conclusions

This work established the wave propagation model that unifies the classical wave propagation equations, the theory of elasticity, the classical laminate theory, the hygrothermal (thermal) effect, and the theory of acoustoelasticity. The results showed the use of the equations proposed by Pao and Gamer [5] and the theory of elasticity, the classical laminate theory for the estimation of the second-order elastic constants, hygrothermal loading, and acoustoelasticity for the estimation of third-order elastic constants. The equations proposed with their

hypothesis are a plausible model that predicts the velocity of longitudinal ultrasonic waves in composite materials. The proposed model will be validated in part B of this study.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Credit author statement

DMG Oliveira: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Formal Analysis; Writing – draft; Experimental procedure. **VV Gonçalves:** Methodology; Formal Analysis; Experimental procedure. **AA Santos Jr.:** Resources; Supervision; Writing review.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank *Espaço da Escrita – Pró-Reitoria de Pesquisa – UNICAMP* — for the language services provided.

References

- [1] Hughes DS, Kelly JL. Second-Order Elastic Deformation of Solids. *Phys Rev* 1953;92:1145–9. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.92.1145>.
- [2] Toupin RA, Bernstein B. Sound Waves in Deformed Perfectly Elastic Materials. Acoustoelastic Effect. *J Acoust Soc Am* 1961;33:216–25. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1908623>.
- [3] Thurston RN, Brugger K. Third-Order Elastic Constants and the Velocity of Small Amplitude Elastic Waves in Homogeneously Stressed Media. *Phys Rev* 1964;133:A1604–10. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.133.A1604>.
- [4] Pao Y, Sachse W, Fukuoka H. Acoustoelasticity and Ultrasonic Measurements of Residual Stresses. In: MASON WP, THURSTON RN, editors. *Phys. Acoust. Vol. 17, Physical Acoustics*; 1984, p. 61–143.
- [5] Pao Y, Gamer U. Acoustoelastic waves in orthotropic media. *J Acoust Soc Am* 1985;77:806–12. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.392384>.
- [6] Egle DM, Bray DE. Measurement of acoustoelastic and third-order elastic constants for rail steel. *J Acoust Soc Am* 1976;60:741–4. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.381146>.
- [7] Jones RM. *Mechanics of Composite Materials*. 2th ed. Taylor e Francis; 1999.
- [8] Every AG. Determination of the elastic constants of anisotropic solids. *NDT E Int* 1994;27:3–10. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0963-8695\(94\)90003-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0963-8695(94)90003-5).
- [9] Tverdokhlebov A. On the acoustoelastic effect. *J Acoust Soc Am* 1983;73:2006–12. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.389567>.
- [10] Lee Y-C, Kim JO, Achenbach JD. Measurement of stresses by line-focus acoustic microscopy. *Ultrasonics* 1994;32:359–65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0041-624X\(94\)90105-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0041-624X(94)90105-8).